

CONTEMPORARY AGRICULTURE
SAVREMENA POLJOPRIVREDA

The Serbian Journal of Agricultural Sciences
Srpski časopis za poljoprivredne nauke

Vol. 64, No. 1 - 2, Pp. 1 - 119, 2015.

www:Contemporary Agriculture
ISSN: 0350-1205 UDC: 63(497.1)(051)-540.2

UNIVERSITAS STUDIORUM
NOVI SAD
NEOPLANTENSIS
University of Novi Sad, Serbia

ПРОГРЕСИВНИ ОДЛУКЕ
1954
УНИВЕРЗИТЕТ У НОВОМ САДУ
Published by
Faculty of Agriculture,
Novi Sad

Case report

UDC: 636.09 : 57.017.7

METABOLIC AND HAEMATOLOGICAL PARAMETERS IN PARETIC COWS THAT RECEIVED OR NOT RECEIVED KETOPROFEN (Case report)*

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Summary: In the period after calving in cows there are many endocrin and metabolic changes because of the increase in energy demand which can cause numerous diseases including puerperal paresis, which is caused by hypocalcemia. The aim of this study was to compare the metabolic and hematological parameters in the first and second week after calving in paretic cows which is administered ketoprofen during three days after calving. Blood samples were taken from cows with postpartum paresis 7 and 14 days after calving. We examined the blood count (number of leukocytes, neutrophils, lymphocytes, red blood cells and hemoglobin concentration) and metabolic profile of cows (total protein, albumin, bilirubin, Ca, P, glucose, cholesterol, AST, GGT, NEFA, BHB). Application ketoprofen does not lead to significant differences in the absolute values of the parameters. However, there was a significant difference in the dynamic changes in the blood picture and metabolism in the second week after birth compared to the first, so that cows that received ketoprofen have less lipid mobilization and ketogenesis, less load hepatocytes and favorable ratio of neutrophils and lymphocytes. We conclude that the use of ketoprofen may be useful as a form of supportive therapy, as it reduces the intensity of lipid mobilization and ketogenesis, and relieves the symptoms of inflammatory response and liver dysfunction in paretic cows.

Key words: ketoprofen, paresis, cows, metabolism, blood count.

INTRODUCTION

During the transition period, the cows go through many physiological adaptations, or endocrine changes due to calving and metabolic changes due to the sharp increase in energy requirements that are necessary for the synthesis of milk (Djokovic et al., 2014). During this period, in order to compensate the shortage of energy in the cow's body fatty acids are mobilized from adipose tissue and are released in the plasma as a non esterified fatty acids (NEFA) (Drackley, 1999; Ingvarsten, 2006). Partial oxidation NEFA then leads to the formation of ketone bodies, which are released from the liver and peripheral tissues are used as the energy source. Reducing the effectiveness of insulin

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*This paper is part of scientific projects TR31062, supported by Ministry of Education and Science, Republic of Serbia.

facilitates the transition of available glucose in the mammary gland to be used as energy for the synthesis of milk (Giesy et al., 2012).

There are many ways in which different disorders during the transition period in cows can trigger an inflammatory response. The acute inflammatory response is associated with changes in lipid metabolism and glucose, which involves increasing lipolysis and NEFA levels (Hardardottir et al., 1994). From the aspect of glucose metabolism, during an acute inflammatory response there is an increase in plasma glucose (Kushibiki et al., 2001). In the period after calving may occur many diseases, most commonly mentioned: ketosis, metritis, mastitis, lameness, abomasum, puerperal paresis and degeneration of the liver (Divers and Peek, 2008). In addition, it comes to significant changes in the metabolism of certain mineral matter where and the most common disorder is puerperal paresis which is developed as a result of hypocalcemia. Factors contributing to the occurrence of hypocalcemia are inability of cows to quickly mobilize enough calcium from the bones and to establish absorption from the small intestine. Beside the metabolic disorders of Ca, causes syndrome recumbent cows may be a metabolic disorder and P, Mg and K, fatty liver, muscle damage, and nerve damage, inflammatory and toxic processes (Djokic et al., 2014).

In veterinary practice, ketoprofen is used to reduce body temperature of animals with fever, to reduce respiratory signs in cows and pigs with pneumonia, to alleviate pain in a variety of conditions such as colic in horses, injuries of joints in horses and dogs, as well as control traumatic and postoperative pain in all animal species (Lees et al., 2004). In a study performed by Donalisio et al. (2013) was found that ketoprofen in comparison with the flunixin-meglumine has similar antiinflammatory effects in cows, or in vitro was noted that the drugs tested reversibly inhibit both isoforms of COX enzymes, but much more COX-1.

The aim of this study is to compare the metabolic and hematological parameters in the first and second week after calving in paretic cows who received ketoprofen.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

In the group of cows that received ketoprofen three cows have developed signs of paresis in the period 24 to 72 hours after calving. That values were compared with a control group of cows that developed paresis and who have not received ketoprofen. Blood samples of the control and experimental groups of cows were taken at 7th and 14th day after calving. We examined the blood count (number of leukocytes, neutrophils, lymphocytes, red blood cells and hemoglobin concentration) and metabolic profile of cows (total protein, albumin, bilirubin, Ca, P, glucose, cholesterol, AST, GGT, NEFA, BHB; Randox reagents). We used a device Siemens ADVIA hematology and biochemical results were obtained on the device type Rayto.

Statistics: the values of haematological and biochemical parameters were presented in the first and second week after calving, the percentage change in the values of the parameters in the second week compared to the first was determined and it was examined whether there is a difference in the dynamics of change in cows received and who are not received ketoprofen.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results show that there are no significant variations in the values of haematological and biochemical parameters in blood of paretic cows who were receiving and who were not receiving ketoprofen. However, the application of ketoprofen leads to differences in the dynamic changes in the blood picture and metabolism in the second week after birth compared to the first as presented in Table 1 and Figure 1. Paretic cows that did not received ketoprofen show an increase in the number of neutrophils and decrease in the number of lymphocytes, with a decrease of albumin concentration, an increase in the concentration of bilirubin, GGT, NEFA and BHB in relation to the paretic cows that received ketoprofen, where they take place opposite processes as presented in Table 1. The more intense inflammatory response characterized by an increase in the number of neutrophils, lymphocytes decline in value and decline in value albumin with increased lipid mobilization and ketogenesis, and there is a greater load hepatocytes probably due to the intense at the accumulation of fat in the liver (which is discussed in greater rise in GGT and more pronounced drop in cholesterol levels in cows that did not receive ketoprofen).

The above results indicate that in cows that did not receive ketoprofen there is intense inflammatory response that in their study confirmed Donalisio et al. (2013). Inflammatory reactions and differential white grapes in cows must be viewed differently, because there are specific blood counts, namely: a high percentage of lymphocytes (60-80%) and little or no reserve of young granulocytes in the bone marrow. During the inflammatory response in cattle occurs in the number of neutrophils with a decline in the total number of leukocytes, but neutropenia and leukopenia were the first signs of acute inflammation. Only after several days accelerates the leukopenia and young neutrophils out of the circulation, but is often clinically undetected due to rapid wear. In acute purulent inflammation guy there

leukopenia, lymphopenia and neutropenia have to turn left. If the animal survives the acute phase compensation occur in the white line, so that the number of neutrophils and lymphocytes decreases, and their relationship becomes inverse (Kovacevic Filipovic, 2007). Here are described changes in the classical inflammatory reaction. Peripartum period demonstrates specific characteristics when the ratio of neutrophils and lymphocytes is in question. The ratio of neutrophils and lymphocytes (N: L ratio) is an important indicator of the health burden and stress of animals (Davis et al., 2005). This relationship in adult cattle is about 0.5:1. In the period around calving there is no typical stress leukogram in cows, which is characterized by neutrophilia, lymphopenia, eosinopenia and variable monoitosis. Acute stress and hypercortisolemia lead to an increase in the concentration of neutrophils dragging these cells into the central pool of blood flow, whereas lymphocytes migrate to the periphery, which leads to the increase in the neutrophil and lymphocyte (N: L ratio is often above 1) (Tornquist and Rigas, 2010). After adaptation to stress N: L ratio returns to the physiological level in the period 2-7 days (Lynch and al., 2010). The value of the relationship N: L is over 1 and it indicates that cows are loaded inflammation or other stressors (Latimer and Prasse, 2003).

Metabolic adaptation of the organism, which is reflected in the intensive mobilization of fats and their use for energy purposes a significant burden on the liver, which can quickly enter the dekompenzacione processes. In fact, higher concentrations of NEFA in the peripartum period ends in the liver where they are exploited for energy purposes. It can be completely metabolized to carbon-4-oxide and water, which provides energy for the liver and physiological functions of the organism. However, it is possible to turn the metabolic processes which burdens the health of the liver and it is: a) partial oxidation of NEFA and production of ketone bodies (especially BHB) going into the circulation and b) NEFA reesterification and the formation of triglycerides that remain in hepatocytes. These two processes often occur together and lead to ketosis cows and fatty infiltration of the liver, which are a major problem in the production and health of cows (Đjokovic, 2010; Šamanac, 2009).

Table 1. Hematology and metabolic findings in paretic cows

	KETOPROFEN						NEGATIVE CONTROL					
	Case 1		Case 2		Case 3		Case 4		Case 5		Case 6	
	Ned1	Ned2	Ned1	Ned2	Ned1	Ned2	Ned1	Ned2	Ned1	Ned2	Ned1	Ned2
WBC x10 ⁹	10,41	10,21	9,05	9,15	6,02	7,39	7,8	9,1	8,2	8,8	8,1	8,9
NEUTRO	6,99	5,48	5,95	5,41	2,53	4,13	4,5	6,1	4	4,7	4,1	5,2
LY	2,53	3,14	2,42	3,3	2,68	2,52	2,6	2,6	3,5	2,9	3,5	2,3
RBC x10 ¹²	5,96	5,48	5,62	5,8	7,03	7,19	6,9	6,5	7,1	6,7	7,2	7,2
Haemoglobine	10,80	10,10	9,2	9,9	10,40	10,60	10,40	9,90	9,87	9,55	9,23	9,23
Platelet	406	213	443	392	394	316	399	401	389	404	412	415
Total protein g/dl	7,0	7,5	6,5	7,0	7,7	7,7	7,1	7,05	7,5	6,9	7,2	6,9
Albumini g/dl	3,3	3,4	2,6	2,6	3,1	3,2	3,1	2,8	3,2	3,05	3	2,75
Total bilirubin	21,1	24,3	12,4	5,8	7,3	12,0	14,5	22,1	9,1	16,7	8,4	15,9
Ca mmol/l	2,4	2,1	2,0	1,9	2,2	2,3	2,1	2,4	2,0	2,3	2,3	2,3
P mmol/l	1,6	1,0	1,5	1,3	1,9	1,9	1,5	1,7	1,6	1,7	1,8	1,8
Glukoza mmol/l	2,7	3,1	3,8	2,6	2,7	3,1	2,5	2,9	2,9	3,3	3,1	2,6
Holesterol mg/dl	104,9	109,9	98,4	78,2	146,6	128,4	106	87,5	99,5	71,5	89,5	81,1
AST IU/L	176,3	389,1	163,7	113,3	114,7	134,3	150	321	98	240	171	299
GGT IU/L	34	22	36	39	31	25	35	39	29	33	28	37
NEFA mmol/l	0,65	0,35	0,5	0,2	0,34	0,31	0,56	0,62	0,51	0,49	0,63	0,58
BHB mmol/l	0,92	0,51	0,83	0,55	0,71	1,1	0,9	1,2	0,84	1,1	0,83	0,99

The change in transcription and protein postranscription contained in VLDL affect the onset of infiltration of liver fat (Bernabucci et al., 2009). Increased mobilization of lipids and their metabolism in the liver with a reduced ability of the liver to produce transport lipoproteins leads to accumulation of lipids in the liver, fatty infiltration and fatty degeneration, which has a negative impact on health and productivity of cows. The most severe form of the disorder called hepatic coma, also known as gravidity toxemia, which usually has a lethal outcome (Djokovic, 2010).

Elevated concentrations of bilirubin in paretic cows that did not receive ketoprofen with intense ketogenesis indicates the existence of load hepatocytes.

Figure 1. The average relative change of selected haematological and biochemical parameters in the second week compared to the first week postpartum in cows receiving (dark line) and who have not received ketoprofen (lighter line).

Although the mechanism of action who helps lipids to induce inflammatory response is not known, there are several ways in which lipids trigger this response. Studies in humans and different animal models confirm the importance of fatty acids as modulators of inflammatory reaction (Calder, 2008; Serhan et al., 2008). Also, many studies have confirmed that excessive amounts of fat and elevated NEFA concentrations represent a positive risk factors for the development of many proinflammatory peripartum diseases in dairy cows, including mastitis and metritis (Bernabucci et al., 2005; Goff, 2006; Douglas et al., 2007).

In their study Trevisi and al. (2009) have confirmed that inflammatory mediators directly induce metabolic changes giving oral interferon- α (cytokine) in the last 2 weeks of gestation, leading to liver inflammation and release of acute phase proteins. Compared to the control group of cows treated cows had significantly higher concentrations in plasma ketones in the first 2 weeks after calving. In other studies, Travis et al. (2001) also estimated the inflammatory response after calving based on the level of albumin, vitamin A (index RBP) and total cholesterol (index lipoprotein) in the blood and developed a composite index of activity of the liver (LAI), with the explanation that the lower the index is, the inflammatory condition greater is the. The same authors (Travis et al., 2010) have shown that cows with higher inflammatory response after calving are characterized by differences in inflammatory markers was expressed in the preceding dry period.

CONCLUSION

According to the statistical analysis, it was noticed that the application of ketoprofen after calving in paretic cows may be useful as a form of supportive therapy. Ketoprofen, as non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug reduces the intensity of lipid mobilization and ketogenesis, and also relieves the symptoms of inflammatory response and liver dysfunction.

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METABOLIČKI I HEMATOLOŠKI NALAZ KOD KRAVA SA POSLEPORODAJNOM PAREZOM KOJE SU PRIMALE ILI NISU PRIMALE KETOPROFEN (Prikaz slučaja)

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Izvod: U periodu posle teljenja kod krava dolazi do brojnih endokrinih i metaboličkih promena zbog povećanja energetske potrebe usled čega mogu nastati brojna oboljenja uključujući i puerperalnu parezu, nastalu kao posledica hipokalcemije. Cilj ove studije je bio da se uporede metabolički i hematološki parametri u prvoj i drugoj nedelji posle teljenja kod paritetnih krava kojima je aplikovan ketoprofen tokom tri dana nakon teljenja. Uzorci krvi su uzeti od krava sa posleporodajnom parezom 7. i 14. dana posle teljenja. Ispitana je krvna slika (broj leukocita, neutrofila, limfocita, eritrocita i koncentracija hemoglobina) i metabolički profil krava (ukupni protein, albumin, bilirubin, Ca,

P, glukoza, holesterol, AST, GGT, NEFA, BHB). Aplikacija ketoprofena ne dovodi do značajnih razlika u apsolutnoj vrednosti parametara. Međutim, nađena je značajna razlika u dinamičnim promenama u krvnoj slici i metabolizmu u drugoj nedelji posle porođaja u odnosu na prvu, tako da kod krava koje su primale ketoprofen postoji manja lipidna mobilizacija i ketogeneza, manje opterećenje hepatocita i povoljan odnos neutrofila i limfocita. Zaključujemo da upotreba ketoprofena može biti korisna kao vid potporne terapije, jer smanjuje intenzitet lipidne mobilizacije i ketogeneze, a ublažava i znake inflamatornog odgovora i disfunkcije jetre kod parturirajućih krava.

Ključne reči: ketoprofen, parturiranje, krave, metabolizam, krvna slika.

Received / *Primljen*: 05.02.2015.

Accepted / *Prihvaćen*: 23.02.2015.